

Planet RDC Program 1.1:

Exemplar Trusted Environmental Data and Information Supply Chains (TEDISCs)

Program Guidelines

The purpose of these guidelines is to provide potential project partners with the program strategy and intended outcomes, and clear guidance around expectations for projects.

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Revision History

Version	Date	Editor	Summary of changes
1.0	26/3/2024	Kerry Levett	Published

Program Overview

The need for trusted data and information supply chains is paramount across research, government, and industry sectors. Researchers require accurate and dependable data to conduct their studies and derive valid conclusions. Governments need reliable data for policy-making, environmental management, and regulatory compliance. Industries require trustworthy data for environmental impact assessments, sustainable resource management, and to meet regulatory standards.

Australia has many excellent producers of data and models. However, there is currently no whole-of-system approach to overcome the challenges of discovering and accessing data and models, assuring their reliability, and the costliness of making them interoperable.

The Trusted Environmental Data and Information Supply Chains (TEDISC) program aims to deliver “trusted environmental data and information supply chains¹” for regional use cases, and the data infrastructure to enable these. The TEDISC program will sit alongside broader work being undertaken by the Australian Government through Environment Information Australia to convene the National Environment Information Supply Chain.

This is a system-wide approach that will support a common view of the capabilities in earth and environmental science data and information supply chains, enabling better alignment of effort and interoperability. The TEDISC program will focus on implementing trust mechanisms across the earth and environmental sectors to facilitate increased data flows between research, government and industry.

Trust needs to be enhanced across the entire information supply chain. This includes data but also the models and analytics that underpin and develop new knowledge and knowledge products. As with data, to ensure reliability and reproducibility, models and their outputs need to be FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable), and the uncertainty in the models needs to be understood.

Three exemplar projects will create TEDISCs for regional use cases. These will be in regions of high biodiversity value, with different pressures on the environment and different stakeholder types. The regional focus is a feasible scale at which to develop partnerships to integrate data and models, while solving real-world problems such as assessing cumulative impact, and mirrors the regional focus of the Government’s Nature Positive Plan².

¹ The [Independent Review of the Environment Protection and Biodiversity Conservation Act](#) highlighted the need for an effective ‘supply chain’ of environmental information. The information required by researchers and decision-makers to understand the environment is obtained through a series of activities that begin with collecting data, then converting raw data through curation and analysis into useful information products. As with more traditional supply chains, each activity can be carried out by a different party, and coordination is needed for an efficient chain that delivers the right products at the right time to the right customers. **A trusted environmental data and information supply chain requires an effective system of data-sharing agreements and information systems that can talk with each other, and reliable data and analytics products.**

² DCCEEW. (2022). *Nature Positive Plan: Better for the environment, better for business.* <https://www.dcceew.gov.au/environment/epbc/publications/nature-positive-plan>

ARDC will work with key research, government and industry stakeholders including DCCEEW, NESP, NEESFF, state agencies, industry partners, Traditional Owners and universities, with a focus on establishing cross-sector partnerships to enable research translation.

TEDSICs can be formed to meet regional use cases, such as:

- Determining the cumulative impacts of developments or other pressures on the environment in a region of Australia
- Providing a transparent and reliable chain of evidence for environmental management and decision-making in a
- Managing and reporting on Country by Traditional Owners, or other land managers
- Efficient and accurate State of Environment reporting

Under the guidance of a single program-level governance committee, each exemplar project will establish an appropriate business model; data governance; practices to make data and software/models FAIR; stakeholder consensus on agreed standards & best practices for data, metadata, vocabularies, data exchange, quality, provenance, and trusted repositories; reliable data and information products and associated supporting digital infrastructure.

The program will have a focus on reusable and repeatable processes and infrastructure enabling TEDISCs to be enabled in other regions faster and more effectively. Business and technology solutions to enable data and model sharing and use will be developed collaboratively across the projects, facilitated by the ARDC. ARDC will provide governance, informatics and technical expertise, and underlying storage and compute infrastructure as appropriate.

Projects in the TEDISC program are expected to collaborate with each other. Project outputs will be published and shared for reuse, and will feed into the National Environment Information Supply Chain framework and toolkit where appropriate.

Other Planet RDC Focus Areas will provide input into the TEDISC program, and data and models will be made available to researchers via Planet RDC infrastructure as appropriate.

Program Outcomes

Key results areas that ARDC will deliver value to research, government and industry through the TEDISC program include:

- A partnership model for government, industry, research and NRI to meet shared data and information needs across multiple earth and environmental science disciplines
- Reusable infrastructure for the secure sharing of data and information to allow TEDISCs to be easily established for other regional use cases
- Strengthening the availability of data for research for priority research questions
- Research translation to government and industry to support evidence-based decision making

- Agreed methods to ensure the reliability and trustworthiness of data and information products³ associated with a region
- Reliable data and information products that form the building blocks for the assessment of cumulative impact, environmental economic accounting, the nature repair market, and accurate environmental prediction and trend reporting.

Project requirements

- Projects must be based on a regional use case that aligns with national priorities and the [Planet RDC program strategy](#), and involves government, industry, research and NCRIS partners
- To ensure the exemplar projects pilot infrastructure and approaches that are broadly applicable to future TEDISCs, the overall project portfolio must cover a range of broad ecosystem types (i.e. terrestrial, marine, freshwater), pressures, and stakeholder groups with diverse needs
- The regional use cases that are selected will require existing partnerships, data capability, and research capability with a reasonable understanding of ecosystems in the region
- The TEDISC should cover multiple disciplines in the earth and environmental sciences
- Projects must seek to develop enduring partnerships needed to support the regional use case
- Infrastructure developed or enhanced during the project is enduring and sustainable after the end of the project
- Existing standards, infrastructure and other resources are expected to be adopted or adapted where possible
- Infrastructure should be available and useful nationally, and where this is not possible (for business model or security reasons) the system must be documented so it can be easily replicated by another TEDISC partnership
- Projects will use the [SAFE guide](#) to support a common view of the capabilities in the TEDISC, to ensure better alignment of effort and interoperability
- Projects must implement trust mechanisms across earth and environmental sectors to facilitate increased data flows between research, government and industry
- Project teams will actively share and collaborate with other TEDISC projects including sharing of outputs, knowledge, communications and infrastructure when relevant

³ 'Information product' is used here to denote the object that is used by an end user, for example a species distribution or groundwater map, or Indigenous Knowledge story, or a decision-support tool that enables a manager or assessor to make a decision. It could also be a dataset or model used by a researcher to do their research.

In Scope Activities

A project to deliver a trusted environmental data and information supply chain (TEDISC) for a regional use case could include the following activities:

- Establishing a TEDISC partnership with regional stakeholders, through workshops and meetings leading to formal agreements
- Defining and implementing the management structure required to operate the TEDISC
- Defining the required 'information products' or other outcomes the TEDISC will deliver for the regional use case
- Mapping the capabilities required to deliver the identified products to the [SAFE](#) framework, and identifying maturity and gaps in those capabilities
- Projects to provide or improve the information products, e.g.
 - Implementing agreed collection protocols, data and metadata standards, vocabularies, identifiers, etc
 - Producing data assets or information products to meet the regional use case
 - Forming consensus on reporting on uncertainty in model outputs and information products
 - Building (or enhancing existing) and operating digital infrastructure(s) to enable the TEDISCs, for example, data spaces based on international standards
- Defining and implementing data governance appropriate to the TEDISC
- Defining criteria for trustworthiness in data and models for the TEDISC
- Collaborating with other TEDISC projects, and reporting on activities and experiences to inform a repeatable model for developing a TEDISC that can be used across other regions
- Other activities as co-designed by ARDC and project stakeholders

Out of Scope Activities

ARDC cannot invest directly in the following (although other exemplar TEDISC partners may provide these outputs as part of the TEDISC):

- Sampling or surveying to fill data gaps
- Research into improving the available models to improve understanding of the regional ecosystem(s)

Process and Timeline

The Planet RDC is following a community [co-design process](#) to deliver its programs.

- 2022 - National consultation and policy analysis identified major national stakeholders and national priorities (see the [Planet RDC Program Description](#)).
- 2023 - Problem identification phase identified priority regional use cases for establishing TEDISCs. These regional use cases meet the Nature Positive Plan’s criteria of regions with “development pressure and with high biodiversity values ... [and] ... a variety of ecosystem types.
- 2024
 - Q1 - Project shaping phase - we will hold workshops and meetings with potential delivery partners and stakeholders to identify and select potential solution(s) and finalise the project team(s)
 - Q2 - Project planning phase, where we will work with identified project partners to develop an investable project plan.

Investment and Duration

The total ARDC budget for the TEDISC program is \$3m.

The ARDC will invest a maximum of \$1m in each exemplar project.

ARDC policy requires a minimum of 1:1 co-investment ratio between ARDC’s investment and that of all the other project participants combined. See the [ARDC’s Co-investment Guidelines](#) for details.

ARDC expectations for the conduct of co-investment projects

- Project partners will match ARDC co-investment at a minimum 1:1 ratio. Both cash and in-kind co-investment are acceptable. All co-investments must be made in an auditable form (see the [ARDC's Co-investment Guidelines](#) for details).
- Projects must be aligned with the [NCRIS 2023 Guidelines](#) and the Principles set out in the [NRI Roadmap](#) (pg 14 pdf, pg 21 doc).
- Projects must have a dedicated project manager with appropriate experience and capacity. Depending on project needs, ARDC may require the naming of a specific Technical Lead and Research.
- Projects must have an ARDC-agreed governance structure to ensure desired outcomes are met. This may require a program-wide steering committee (including members not directly involved in the delivery of the projects) with defined Terms of Reference that meets at least quarterly. Depending on project needs, ARDC may require the formation of a user reference group.
- Projects are required to commit to monthly traffic light reporting and other reporting requirements specified at contracting.
- Project plans must include the tracking of desired outcomes, including measuring the uptake of infrastructure by the research community, industry and government with clear KPIs that evidence the value to research, government and industry.
- Project plans should include user testing of ideas and prototype outputs early and often throughout project delivery.
- Most outputs will require ongoing operation beyond the life of the project in order to realise the intended benefits. Project plans must include a statement of the minimum ongoing maintenance likely to be required (both duration and resources) and a plan for that maintenance (to be agreed between ARDC and the project partners).
- Project outputs (including software) should be made as FAIR as possible, and the infrastructure developed should make research outputs FAIR for reuse and reproducibility. See the [ARDC guideline for FAIR data](#), [FAIR for Research Software](#), and [FAIR for Virtual Research Environments](#).
- Project teams are expected to collaborate across the Planet RDC and other ARDC-supported projects, as relevant and directed by the ARDC, to meet program objectives.
- Project teams are expected to attend and contribute to relevant ARDC workshops and events.
- Project teams are expected to engage in communication activities to raise awareness of their project and attract a growing user base within the earth and environmental sciences community. When doing so, projects need to acknowledge ARDC and NCRIS using the wording [provided by ARDC](#).